

**Improving services and raising competitiveness in Azerbaijan's health and wellness tourism
(with considering the foreign experience)**

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Abstract: Health and wellness tourism is one of the promising subsectors of Azerbaijan's tourism industry. Based on various natural resources of high healing significance, a series of sanatoriums, resorts and smaller health facilities have been created in the country in the last 20 years. However, the existing potential of health and wellness tourism is not efficiently used. One of the main reasons for this are the gaps directly related to organization of services at health and wellness tourism enterprises. As the official statistics shows, the number of visitors spending ten days and more at these health tourism facilities purely for treatment purposes is low in the country. Problems available are due to insufficient and poor application of successful health tourism models of other countries, as well as imperfect marketing, insufficient promotion of therapeutic muds and mineral springs, and inability to offer more attractive tourism products in the market.

This paper explores both the gaps and improvement possibilities in services offered in the health and wellness tourism of Azerbaijan, with exploring and emphasizing the health and wellness tourism subsectors of the Russian Federation and Georgia, the country's two neighbors. The research highlights the opportunities for improving of marketing strategy and the raising of the quality of services and touristic products in the country's health and wellness tourism, with taking into account the foreign experience. It broadly focuses on how entrepreneurs in health and wellness tourism should operate to increase their competitive capacity and thus ensure the success in the market. The research is of practical importance to scientists, tourism managers, practitioners, entrepreneurs and investors.

Keywords: *health tourism, wellness, sanatorium, tourism marketing, resort*

Introduction. Health and wellness tourism is one of rapidly growing subsectors of the modern health industry. It is a high-growth market segment in the modern international tourism, associated with improving of visitors' health, involvement in spa, nutrition exercises, fitness, spiritual well-being, meditation, yoga, etc. (Lee, 2024; Andreu et al, 2021). It provides an opportunity to prevent the adverse impact of various diseases and mental health problems. The increasing share of aged tourists influences health and wellness tourism, thus significantly stimulating the creation of niche market (WTO & ETC, 2018). The development of wellness directly and indirectly contributes to improving of socioeconomic development of regions, accessibility of healthcare services, catering businesses, physical environment, host communities, etc. (Liao et al., 2023; Mueller, Kaufmann, 2001; Imrani et al., 2024).

Profitability and efficiency of operation of health tourism enterprises directly depend on the adequateness of their customer-involving policy: the higher the interest to the offered health services, the higher number of tourists is attracted to services offered by tourism businesses in the market. In Azerbaijan, the number of those using the services of sanatorium- and resort type enterprises is relatively low, and this is significantly due to the fact that that considerable part of regular customers of health tourism services are those recovering their health in foreign countries.

The mineralogical and other natural resources of healing- and wellness importance are rich in Azerbaijan. Using of this resource potential of high tourism importance is relevant forty five (Karimov, Musayev, 2022). Health tourism facilities are capable to take advantage of this potential through increasing of the level and range of their services with taking into account also the current situation in the market and expanding their touristic products associated with these natural treatment resources (Karimov, Dargahov, 2017). Meantime, in order to make tourist flows to head to domestic health tourism facilities but not to beyond the country's boundaries, it is necessary condition to effectively organize and improve health services in compliance to the needs of modern tourists.

The goal of this research is to develop recommendations on quality of services, preparation of touristic product and marketing in the health and wellness tourism of Azerbaijan. The research makes an emphasis on the incorporation from the experiences of Russia and Georgia, the countries that are also

trying to modernize their resort and sanatorium infrastructures inherited from the Soviet period. The paper is largely focused on the increasing of the competitive potential of Azerbaijan's health and wellness tourism businesses through marketing policy and diversification of touristic product in the market.

Methodology. To carry out this research, the methods and approaches such as literature review, analysis of report data, conduction of analogy, diagnostic assessment, and comparative analysis were involved and addressed. To develop recommendations on the improvement of health and wellness tourism in Azerbaijan, first the gaps and shortcomings present in this subsector are identified and explored with considering the concept and principles of this type of tourism industry as a prerequisite. The next phase of this study was the assessment of enterprises operating in the field of health and wellness tourism from view of satisfying the interests of customers and successfully competing in the market. For this assessment, various data shown in research papers and project reports served as a source of information. Then the obtained data was analysed and summarized with emphasizing the most important agents and conditions influencing the explored subsector of tourism. Further the marketing policy and operation features of wellness tourism industries of other neighbor countries were investigated, analysed and compared with those of Azerbaijan by the points where similar activities and priorities of operation are present. As similar cases, health and wellness tourism industries of the Russian Federation and Georgia were addressed and explored. Based on the explorations and comparative analysis, the recommendations on the improvement of services in health and wellness tourism of Azerbaijan are offered.

Problems and gaps in health and wellness tourism of Azerbaijan. The wellness and health tourism industry of Azerbaijan developed relatively rapidly in the last two decades (Dargahov, Karimov, 2011). A few large and luxury health tourism enterprises serving domestic and also foreign tourists have been commissioned in various parts of the country (Dargahov, Karimov, 2014). These health and wellness tourism enterprises include, for example, the sanatorium area of Naftalan resort operating on the basis of special healing oil resource, as well as the Lankaran-Istisu and Qafqaz Thermal and Spa Resort Hotel specializing in various wellness-related services due to rich mineral and thermal waters found. As the mentioned sanatoriums and resorts have established a high-level service, Azerbaijan's wellness and health tourism industry is one of most developed in the Caucasus region today (Soltanova et al, 2017).

However, the problems in this subsector remains. A number of gaps are typical for the wellness and health tourism industry of Azerbaijan. Most of them are related to the existence of inadequate infrastructure (e.g. transport facilities), weak promotion and marketing, and a lack of qualified personnel in the country's regions. Other challenges include the overall ineffective policy in this field, the service quality issues, as well as the limited contribution of travel agencies in promoting health tourism packages.

With taking into account the situation with the availability of potential customers in the market as well as the traditions "established" in the tourism market of Azerbaijan, the current scale of coverage of the preferential "vouchers", traditionally playing very important role in the involvement of public sector employees in the health and wellness tourism in the country, cannot be satisfactory. The clients of the voucher system typically include same beneficiaries of health services each year, while most of employees that potentially would be beneficiaries of such vouchers also, remain unaware of this opportunity. This is the result of bureaucracy at the enterprise level, inefficient promotion and marketing, and also the weakness of cooperations between various stakeholders. The involvement of mostly aged employees but not the young potential beneficiaries in health and wellness tourism is in part related to these gaps as well.

While the Soviet-style sanatorium rest is based on the "economic-class" and discount-based rest of retirees or those on the verge of retirement with limited income, and the leisure consists of almost exclusively of therapeutic medical procedures, the modern-style sanatorium rest in practice implies the hosting and serving of middle and younger age tourists in modern spa hotels or sanatoriums offering high-quality services. In Azerbaijan, resting in a sanatorium is largely associated with the first, "inherited" type. Thus, in the country, customers in health and wellness tourism are mainly elderly people, over sixty years old as usual, whereas in many countries it is about forty-five to fifty years.

The experience of foreign countries. The experience of other neighbor countries in the field of health and wellness tourism was analysed in this paper. The first case is the health and wellness tourism of the **Russian Federation**. The health tourism market of Russia shares many similarities with that of

Azerbaijan, since they both have large Soviet-style sanatorium traditions and own same common natural treatment resources such as mineral waters.

In the Russian Federation, the health and leisure opportunities are typically offered as a single touristic product associated with the involvement of natural resource factor in its content. Visitors using the touristic products comprising of the healing component have an opportunity to be treated in medical facilities and recover their health, satisfying their aesthetic needs as well. Through effectively using of the available resource potential, an increase in demand for local tourism products in the domestic and post-Soviet markets is achieved.

The cooperation between the state and the private sector in the field of health tourism is another typical feature of health and wellness tourism industry of Russia. Thus, the experience of the European countries (Germany, Italy, Czech Republic, Slovakia, Poland, Slovenia, etc.) in the health tourism is incorporated. The joint participation of both sectors in the construction of most of the new sanatoriums and tourist facilities is remarkable. The government has adopted a special program to accelerate the development of medical and health tourism, including resorts and sanatoriums (The Federal Program on Developing Domestic and Foreign Incoming Tourism in the Russian Federation for 2011–2018), which encourages the private sector to play a more active role in this field (providing necessary infrastructure etc.). Other similar programs have been adopted at the regional level. Involvement of businesses in this sub-sector in addition to the state support seems effective in terms of improving of the quality of relevant services (Oborin, 2022).

Through the “putyovka” (voucher-based) scheme, the sanatorium-resort services are provided for visitors working in the public sector. These services for long have been an integral part of the “polyclinic–hospital–sanatorium” system. In modern times, the development of medical and health tourism in the country still is largely based on this tradition. The existing infrastructure has been reconstructed in compliancy with the modern standards (Manshina, 2014).

Meantime, the sanatoriums in Russia typically benefit tourists from the post-Soviet countries, considering the preferential price factor for customers with medium budget. Special attention is also paid to the marketing of mountain resorts and recreational facilities of high health tourism importance operating on the basis of thermal springs. Cooperation with hundreds of travel agencies involving customers has been established. The seasonality factor in the price policy is considered, too.

Several mechanisms toward travel packages sale are in use in the domestic market in Russia: direct sales to enterprises, state and municipal funds and also social protection bodies; implementation through tourism companies; provision of services to regular customers without spending on advertising, etc. In practice, many resort organizations in Russia are using each of the above tools simultaneously. Natural resources such as healing muds, radon waters etc. of treatment importance are largely based in the operations of Russia’s well-known resorts (in Kislovodsk, Yessentuki, Pyatigorsk, Zheleznovodsk (the Caucasus Mineral Waters region), as well as those situated in Kabardino-Balkaria and Karachay-Cherkessia). The resorts in the Caucasian part of Russia have successfully combined the “low price” component with the “medium service” factor. The spa services have been added to the packages as well (Горбунов et al., 2016). The success has been achieved also due to the establishment of specialized sportswear stores, clubs oriented on various tourist interests, horse-riding tours, rafting tours, special trekking programs, etc. serving tourists. Eventually various tour companies are involved in these operations in the Caucasus Mineral Waters region. A survey found that about 20% of the hosted vacationers aged 20-39 in the region have a great need for additional services in their leisure and are interested in “energy-intensive” recreational services. The autumn season is considered more favorable for sanatorium- and resort treatment as the number of vacationers during this period is less than in summer. 75% of vacationers are women and most of them are 35-50 years old. (Novoselova et al. 2017). **Georgia**, another neighbor of Azerbaijan has improved its health and wellness tourism in recent years. In this country, the very basic forms of resort service have been transformed: sanatoriums and pensions with their relatively larger and medically trained personnel were replaced by accommodations of various size and kinds, where visitors with health concerns stay side by side with other guests of different age resting on a regular basis, while the treatment is accessible at adjacent medical centers, clinics, baths, etc. (Tutberidze, 2021). Both governmental and private investments are involved in the country’s health tourism.

Resorts in Georgia are in search of ways to make the offered touristic products diversified to attract more investments. In this regard, with keeping the curative functions of health and wellness enterprises, management organizes sport events, interesting cultural programs, various wellness procedures and health improvement services such as anti-stress, phito-rejuvenation, anti-cellulite,

cosmetology, etc.). The practice of combining of natural healing with traditional practices is widely found in Georgia. This includes a range of experiences, from traditional treatments to modern spa therapies, often incorporating local herbal medicine, aromatherapy, and organic cuisine within scenic and tranquil environments (Metreveli et al., 2025).

Georgian wellness tourism enterprises typically use a range of marketing strategies including digital marketing (SEO, social media), public relations (PR), strategic partnerships, and traditional marketing to promote their services. These efforts focus on building brand awareness, highlighting specific offerings like balneotherapy and eco-tourism, and reaching target audiences through online channels and industry collaborations. Djakeli (2018) notes that entrepreneurs without experience in healthcare are trying to address the cost leadership strategy, the strategy of cost focus and also the penetration marketing strategy. The travel agencies in Georgia's wellness tourism make an effort to attract tourists with offering them low prices for services – 10 to 40% discount (Gvelesiani et al., 2014). Balneological resorts in Tbilisi and other cities offer mud baths, therapeutic massage based on resources of healing importance. Children suffering from autism are served, too. In the medical and wellness resort Bioli, individual health programs are developed to serve visitors on the basis of innovative methods of diagnostics and scientifically based algorithm. After treatment procedures, patients are re-diagnosed to determine the “before” and “after” results. Special free services and some of therapeutic procedures are provided to customers staying for 7 nights or more at the four-star Borjomi Palace hotel. Special attention is paid to the arrangement of the ski resort infrastructure. The development of the resort has been regulated based on the adopted pre-requisite documents such as General Land Use Plan of Borjomi outlining mineral water deposit sanitary zones, as well as on Borjomi Local Development Strategy 2016-2019 and the official management documents for Borjomi municipality (Khoshtaria et al., 2019). The adoption of such documents contributed to efficiently using of the existing resource potential in the resort area. This experience indicates to the importance of the adoption of development documents specifically designed for resort areas having high wellness tourism importance and experience.

To attract visitors in the market, the famous Georgian sanatorium of Tskaltubo diversifies its serviced associated with treatments on the basis of mineral waters, aqua aerobics, underwater hydromassage, charcot showering, physiotherapy, and horizontal underwater traction of spine. Meantime, gynecological and peloidotherapeutic services are offered. The treatment of musculoskeletal system, cardiovascular and nervous system, metabolic disorders, venereal, skin- and other diseases is organized. The “all inclusive” package of services is offered to customers, while entertainment program, outdoor pool opportunities, etc. are included as well. In addition to the most necessary sanatorium infrastructure, the development strategy of Tskaltubo also includes the creation of playgrounds, a water park, a tropical garden, golf and basketball courts, a park for sliding, a shopping center, cafes, bars and restaurants.

Recommendations. Based on the analysis of the existing health and wellness tourism market of Azerbaijan as well as the experience of Russia and Georgia in same field, the conducted research provides certain recommendations on the improvement of services and raising of competitiveness in this subsector of Azerbaijan's tourism.

In overall sense, the main goal of health tourism industries in Azerbaijan should include attracting of vacationers interested in recovering their health based on natural healing means while the significant part of them still currently prefers buying the similar touristic products at the resorts of foreign countries.

In Azerbaijan, the vast majority of potential customers who benefit from health tourism services are mainly those suffering from certain chronic diseases, mainly elderly people. However, this should not be the case. The clientele in health and wellness tourism should not be comprised of those only who suffer from early signs of diseases rather all the age groups should be a part of this industry. The case that elderly and sick people make up the majority of the clients of health tourism facilities means the marketing doesn't work adequately. From this point of view, it is necessary to attract customers of other age groups as well, both men and women, with achieving an increase in the number of family vacationers (Karimov, Musayev, 2022). In order to break the unfavorable stereotypes mentioned above in practice, the range and quality of services offered in health and wellness tourism market should be increased and improved. Large health tourism enterprises and institutions should own their highly designed and flexible websites suitable for interactive communication.

While in many foreign countries, in particular in the economically developed ones, health and recreation facilities have long included activities aiming the satisfaction of the individual recreational

needs in their marketing, in Azerbaijan, this component is relatively poorly developed. In this regard, resorts and sanatoriums should not neglect the fact that some of these services should be customized (personalized). The diversification of services makes sense, too. It should be taken into account that by diversifying and improving the services offered in sanatoriums, the seasonality context of health tourism product is fairly reduced, allowing the involvement of a wide range of different tourist segments all year round. E.g. it is important for health tourism enterprises to offer dietary nutrition package since some of overweight vacationers or those who may have such a risk prefer dietary foods on a daily basis and are interested in continuing with the same diet at the destination.

Private health and tourism facilities launching their businesses in health and wellness tourism should not hastily purchase expensive medical equipment rather they should carefully consider the profitability, explore the situation in the market, correctly assess the purchasing power of customers and their interests toward these services, as well as consider the availability of necessary personnel and know whether the new equipment will be truly profitable, and the expected efficiency will be reached. The increase in service fees shouldn't become a force that "turns the customer away". Healthcare institutions should take corporate goals into account when determining their costs and service prices.

Services offered in wellness tourism facilities should be accessible in due time, e.g. the fact that the fitness center of a sanatorium is open until 5 or 6 o'clock may not matter to a patient served with medical procedures by that time and thus being physically incapable to benefit from that fitness service. Specialized sanatoriums should be equipped with SPA complexes (bath treatments, artificial salt cave-based halotherapy, etc.) and thus increase their competitiveness in the market.

Another important component is related to aesthetic context of a place where clients stay and have a rest (Karimov, Dargahov, 2017). The relaxation environment should be improved: e.g. architecture of building, and color of interior walls should be appropriate, flexibility in receiving patients should be ensured, etc. The old buildings of sanatoriums inherited from the Soviet era or the design reminiscent of it do not correspond to the taste of modern-day clientele. Nowadays, the requirements with respect to design, size of a room, state and quality of a building, furniture and accessories available, the most minimal infrastructure, sanitary facilities, bath- and shower rooms, etc. are different than that of previous decades. Sanatorium and their beds should avoid reminding a hospital environment. A patient should feel that the sanatorium chosen by him/her really provides services compliant with modern requirements, where strict organization, orderliness, and accuracy by each service is present. In particular, the feeling of hospitality of staff toward the visitors makes sense.

With respect to choosing health tourism destination online, as the practice shows, vacationers prefer mainly health facilities with a higher reputation. A good reputation is indeed earned if the quality of services provided by the sanatorium and if the treatment meets the expectations of vacationers over a long period of time. However, the noted shouldn't lessen the importance of successful marketing. It should be emphasized that typically most of customers makes their choice based on recommendations of their friends and relatives who have had some experience as vacationers in health tourism.

A study conducted in Russia concluded that the price factor is more important for certain tourist segments when choosing a sanatorium. Thus, it was turned out that the choice by most customers is made in favor of a touristic product and a discounted package with reasonable price though they are aware of the fact that some establishments with a great reputation offer higher quality services. Customers who choose the price factor in some cases even "forget" to pay due attention to the quality of service.

Customers of sanatorium facilities are divided into two large groups – vacationers (1) using treatment and health services on a (discounted) basis, thus representing the "middle class", and relatively high-income tourists (2) using the same type of services at their own expense. Taking into account the existence of the two corresponding "parallel markets", it is important for sanatoriums of higher demand in the market to distinguish the operation by two (pick and non-pick) seasons of a year, which means the wider acceptance of socially oriented tourist flows should be targeted in winter while the priority should be maintained toward hosting the second, high-income segment of tourists in summer, when the demand is higher. Such a practice is widely used in sanatoriums in a number of countries. Another experience is that in these countries regional programs are adopted for resort areas as well where the seasonality is evidently observed.

The tradition of providing sanatorium services on the basis of (discounted) travel packages (vouchers) should be preserved in any case as this factor ensures the continuous arrival of a significant number of relatively low-income tourists to sanatoriums and resort facilities. If vacationers are satisfied with the services, they turn to these sanatoriums the next season.

Also, it is recommended that health tourism facilities, including those operating on the basis of healing mineral waters and mud, to include internationally certified services in their activities and also to widely use alternative therapies. This is important not only in terms of ensuring successfulness of the tourism operations and thus increasing competition in the market and the quality of service, but also from view of mitigating the large tourist flows seeking treatment and health care abroad rather than in the domestic market.

The resorts and sanatoriums in Azerbaijan should pay much attention to the development of additional services, which they have not paid enough attention to so far. This is important since the vacationers resting in resorts are interested not only in basic services, but also in additional services. After leaving the resort, vacationers typically share the impressions of their vacation among their relatives and friends: impressions associated with additional services are not forgotten, being remembered for a long time. This potentially creates additional demand for health and wellness services in the market.

It is important to include at least several additional services in tourism package, considering the availability of choice. Meantime, individual tour products should be designed for approximately same age groups, and should ensure that tourists are enthusiastic about spending time together. For example, additional services should not consist only of traditional services – excursions, acquaintance with local natural landscapes but should at least partially be of an entertaining nature in content (e.g. team games with support of a guide or competitive games with symbolic awarding). A survey conducted in one of the Mineralnye Vody sanatoriums of Russia found the visitors' interests to such games.

Organizing “cheap service weeks” under the campaign like “cheap and quality rest”, “20% of your vacation fee from us”, etc. can be one of the components of the marketing strategy as well. The creation of a database called “our regular customers” by resorts and sanatoriums, and the issuance of a special bonus coupon for these regular customers, valid for a year and providing preferential access to basic or additional services, can also be applied as part of the incentive strategy of health facilities.

The importance of healing muds and well-known mineral springs found in Azerbaijan should be promoted more actively since there is a quite high competition in the international (regional) markets of spa tourism, fitness tourism and wellness tourism. Promotional work should be carried out to attract tourists from the post-Soviet countries, as well as from the countries with different natural conditions, such as Iraq, the UAE, Saudi Arabia etc. The introduction of a star category for sanatorium institutions in Azerbaijan would be possible, too. Before this, there will be a need to increase the number of competing entities in this field, expand the market and strengthen the competition.

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